

TA'LIM SOHASIDA XALQARO HAMKORLIK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10695268>

Annotatsiya. Biz bugun yoshlarga qanchalik yetarli bilim bersak, ma'naviy – madaniy merosimizdan bahramand etsak, zamonaviy madaniyat yutuqlarini o'rgatsak, ular shunchalik mustaqil davlatimiz rivojiga, jamiyatni yangilash, moderni-zatsiyalashga tayyor bo'ladi va shunga intiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: TESIS, FONTIS Universiteti, BMT, ABU Konsalt, AKSELS.

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

Abstract. The more we give young people enough knowledge, enjoy our spiritual and cultural heritage, and teach them the achievements of modern culture, the more they will be ready for the development of our independent state, the renewal and modernization of society, and they will strive for it.

Keywords: TESIS, FONTIS University, BMT, ABU Consult, AKSELS.

МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО В СФЕРЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. Чем больше мы будем давать молодым людям достаточно знаний, пользоваться нашим духовным и культурным наследием, обучать их достижениям современной культуры, тем больше они будут готовы к развитию нашего независимого государства, к обновлению и модернизации общества, будет стремиться к этому.

Ключевые слова: ТАСИС, Университет ФОНТИС, BMT, ABU Consult, AKSELS.

Mustaqillik yillarda davlatning iqtisodiyotga aralashuvi birmuncha kamaydi.

Respublikamizda iqtisodiyotni erkinlashtirish bo'yicha belgilangan vazifalar ta'lim sohasida ham amalga oshirilmoqda. O'zbekistonning BMT doirasida jahon mamlakatlari bilan hamkorligi ilmiy, texnik, madaniy, ma'rifiy, ma'naviy sohalardagi ko'p qirrali aloqalar xalqimizning yaqinlashuvida qimmatli ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bu aloqalar gumanizm, insonparvarlik, do'stlik, o'zaro hamkorlik ruhini mustahkamlash bilan bir qatorda davlatlararo iqtisodiy-siyosiy munosabatlarni mustahkamlashga, ta'lim tizimining barqaror rivojlanishiga, davlatlarning gullab-yashnashiga xizmat qilmoqda.

Mustaqillikning ilk yillaridan boshlab respublikamizda ta'lim sohasida xorijiy tajribalarni o'rganish, ular bilan ishlash yuzasidan muayyan tajriba to'plandi. Milliy kuzatish markazi, shuningdek, TESIS ning «Ta'lim tizimini isloh qilishda Xalq ta'limi vazirligi hamda Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligiga ko'maklashish» loyihalari buning yorqin misolidir.

Mazkur loyihaning asosiy kontraktori Niderlandiyadagi – FONTIS Universitetidir.

Loyihada Buyuk Britaniya Kengashi va ABU Konsalt, Niderlandiya, Belgiya, Buyuk Britaniya, Germaniya, Polsha, Vengriya, Rossiyadan xorijiy ekspertlar qatnashadi. Loyiha ta'limni rivojlantirishning besh yo'nalishini: qonunchilik, boshqaruv, moliyalashtirish, bilimlarning sifati va ularga baho berish hamda axborotlashtirishni nazarda tutadi.

Respublikamizda 1992 yil fevral oyidan boshlab BMT doirasida «Ozbekistonda boshlang'ich kasb tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishni qo'llab – quvvatlash» loyishasi amalga oshirish boshlandi. O'zbekistonda ayrim mutaxas-sisliklar bo'yicha o'qitish, tayyorlash turlarini keng qamrovli joriy etish loyishaning maqsadidir. 1993 yilda taxminan 3,0 mln. Germaniya markasidan 15 % o'quv yurtlarini zarur asbob-uskunalar jishozlash uchun ajratildi.¹

1997-1999 yillarda Yaponiya hukumatining imtiyozli narx krediti bo'yicha manfaatdor yapon kompaniyalari bilan hamkorlikda 200,0 mln. AQSh dollari miqdorida moliyalashtirildi. Loyishani kreditlashning muddati qirq yil bo'lishi taxmin qilinmoqda. Hozirda ushbu mablag'larni maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarini tegishli asbob – uskunalar bilan ta'minlashga, ularning moddiy – texnik bazasini mustashkamlashga, yetkazib berilayotgan asbob – uskunalarining mushandis – texnik tomonidan o'zlashtirib olinishiga yo'naltirish nazarda tutilmoqda.

Shu o'tgan qisqa davr ichida Respublikamiz ta'lim taraqqiyotini ta'minlay oladigan darajada ko'pgina ijobiy, muvaffaqiyatlar qo'lga kiritildi. Bu borada Navoiy viloyat xalq ta'limining ham o'z o'rnini, salohiyati, bor. Shu o'rinda viloyat mutasaddi tashkilotlarining tashabbuskorligini qayd etish joiz.

Jumladan, “Ta'lim to'g'risida”gi qonun, “Kadrlar tayyorlash Milliy dasturi” qabul qilinganga qadar ham bizda maktabgacha tarbiya to'g'risida biryoqlama fikr yuritib kelgan edi. Bugun esa avvalgidan farqli ravishda bu masalaga, biz chuqurroq va yangicha mas'uliyat bilan yondashmoqdamiz. So'nggi yillarda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining yangi tarmoqlari, oilaviy ta'limning ko'rinishlaridan biri – “Xonadon bog'chasi” shuningdek, “Bolalar bog'chasi - boshlang'ich maktab” majmualarini tashkil topganligini ta'kidlash o'rinlidir. Oz fursat ichida viloyatimizda bunday bog'chalar ko'plab tashkil etilgan.

Mustaqillik yillarida viloyatimiz maktabgacha tarbiya tarkibida ham katta o'zgarishlar amalga oshirildi. Istiqloq sharofati bilan 22 ta yangi turdagi ta'lim muassasalari tashkil topdi, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari huzurida maktabga tayorlash yo'nalishdagi sinflar faoliyat boshladi.

Istiqloq sharofati bilan, ta'lim soshasida xalqaro hamkorlik uchun keng yo'l ochildi, ta'lim va til o'rganish bo'yicha AKSELS tashkilotining ko'p bosqichli tanlovlarida Navoiy hashar o'quvchilaridan so'nggi 4 yil davomida ishtirok etgan va g'oliblik shohsupasiga ko'tarilgan 11 nafar o'quvchi Amerikaning turli shtatlarida ta'lim olib qaytishdi.¹ Bular kechagina boh'cha tarbiyalanuvchilari edi. Hozirgi kunlarda viloyatimizning sobiq o'quvchilari bo'lmish Xudoyorov Ixtiyor, (Zarafshon shashri), Sharipov Bashodir (Qiziltepa tumani) Faxriddinov Ma'ruf (Xatirchi tumani) Yo'ldoshev Shamsiddin (Xatirchi tumani) lar “Umid” jamg'armasi orqali o'zlarining puxta bilimini namoyish etgan sholda xorijiy mamlakatlar (Fransiya va AQSh) ning o'quv yurtlarida tahsilni tugatib ish faoliyatini o'zning jonajon yurtida davom ettirmoqdalar.¹

Bugungi kunda viloyat Xalq ta'limi boshqarmasi 11 ta xalqaro tashkilot

¹ Мустақиллик одимлари, ислохотдаги туб бурилишлар ва натижалар.Навоий.2001. 3-6

¹ Мустақиллик одимлари, ислохотдаги туб бурилишлар ва натижалар.Навоий.2001. 4-6

¹ Мустақиллик одимлари, ислохотдаги туб бурилишлар ва натижалар.Навоий.2001.23-6

bilan shamkorlik o`rnatgani o`z samarasini berayotgani faxrlidir. Xalqaro tashkilotlar BMT doirasida beminnat yordam ko`rsatib kelayotganligi natijasida sohaning moddiy-texnika bazasi mustahkamlanib, jahon andozalari, zamonaviy o`quv qurollari bilan jihozlanmoqda.

Biz bugun yoshlarga qanchalik yetarli bilim bersak, ma`naviy – madaniy merosimizdan bahramand etsak, zamonaviy madaniyat yutuqlarini o`rgatsak, ular shunchalik mustaqil davlatimiz rivojiga, jamiyatni yangilash, moderni-zatsiyalashga tayyor bo`ladi va shunga intiladi.

Yoshlarni dunyoga chiqishlari uchun bilim sirlarini puxta egallashlari hamda jahon hamjamiyatida mamlakatimiz obro`sini mustahkamlash maqsadida 2012 yil 10 dekabrda O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Chet tillarni o`rganish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to`g`risida”gi qarori qabul qilindi. Qarorda zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalangan holda o`qitishning ilg`or uslublarini joriy etish yo`li bilan yosh avlodning chet tillarda erkin so`zlasha oladigan qilib o`qitishning huquqiy asoslari yaratildi. Bu jarayon maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalaridan boshlab o`yin tarzidagi darslar o`tkazish, asosan ingliz tilini o`rganish, mutaxassis o`qituvchi va murabbiylarni bog`chalarga ko`proq jalb etish masalalariga katta e`tibor qaratildi.

Davlatimizning yosh pedagog va murabbiylarga g`amg`o`rlik ko`rsatishi, ularni huquqiy va ijtimoiy jihatdan himoya qilish, milliy-madaniy an`analarning avloddan-avlodga o`tishi hamda ma`naviy aloqalarni ta`minlash, eng muhimi chet el mamlakatlari yoshlari bilan bellasha oladigan, o`sha tilda raqobatlasha oladigan komil insonni tarbiyalash bosh vazifa qilib belgilandi.

Zero, yoshlarimizning faoliyati yanada yorqinroq bo`lishi e`tirof etilmoqda.

Ta`lim soshasida bozor iqtisodiyoti munosabatlarini shakllantirishni rivojlan-tirish va takomillashtirish borasida, fermer, soliq, bojxona, auditlardan iborat yangi kasblarni yoshlarga bolaligidan o`rgatish maqsadida Navoiy shashridagi maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarining 4 – 11 –16 bog`chalarida tarqatma material-lar asosida mashg`ulotlar o`tkazish yo`lga qo`yilgan.

Modernizatsiya – zamonaviylashtirish, eng so`nggi innovatsion g`oyalar, yangi pedagogik ta`lim tizimini joriy etish - fan – texnika yutuqlarini hayotga tadbir etish demak.

Yoshlarimiz katta avlodga xos bo`lgan mahdudlikni, qoloq texnologiyalar sharoitida shakillangan psixologiyaning nomukammalligidan xalos bo`lishi, ularda sog`lom milliy iftixor, g`urur, “men hech kimdan kam emasman” degan tuyg`u shakllanishi, eng muhimi ijtimoiy qo`rquv bo`lmasligi kerak.¹ Zero, o`z-o`zidan ayonki, har bir avlod jamiyat taraqqiyotiga, uning moddiy va ma`naviy yuksalishiga o`z hissasini qo`shib, ilm–fanni boyitadi, yangi texnologiyalar yaratadi. Bu esa, kichik bolalik paytidan boshlab yoshlarimizni ana shu yangi texnologiyalar bilan qurollantirish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqarmoqda.

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